

Statistical Analysis of Election Fraud in Serbia: Case Study Beograd

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1. Introduction

Elections in Serbia have long been considered rife with different forms of election fraud: voter manipulation and intimidation, “phantom” voters, buying votes, etc. However, to this author’s best knowledge, there has been no significant examination of voting patterns to try to establish some reliable metrics to gauge election fraud. This article represents an effort to address election fraud using universal statistical metrics like voter turnout trends, identify patterns potentially corresponding with certain types of abuse, and provide a simple and robust model for election fraud detection.

I will be looking at several factors: changes in voter rolls, both between individual elections and over longer periods, changes in voter turnout normalized to reported or projected adult population based on the census data, and correlations between voter turnout in Belgrade overall and individual municipalities, as well as correlations in voter turnout between individual municipalities. I will compare two periods: 2003-2012 and 2014-2024 to show how significant changes in statistical trends can be viewed as an indicator of election fraud, and how to use the magnitude of these changes to estimate the extent of election fraud.

2. Population and voter rolls

Table 1. shows the projected adult population in Belgrade and individual municipalities from 2003 to 2024, based on the census data from 2002, 2011, and 2022. Population estimates were done using simple linear extrapolations for the relevant inter-census period. Post 2022 population estimate was conducted by extrapolating the 2011-2022 population trends. The expected errors should be relatively small, especially for post 2011 period, due to relatively small population changes and consistent population trends in most municipalities. One potential source of error is that Surcin municipality was created in 2003, and, therefore, was still part of Zemun municipality for both the 2002 census and 2003 elections. However, 2002 census data contains detailed information, including separate population counts for Surcin as part of Zemun. 2003 election data was projected under the assumption that the turnout distribution was the same as in 2007, when Surcin was independent municipality, taking into account population changes.

The population census data will be used throughout this paper to normalize voting population, under the assumption that any inaccuracies in voter rolls (deceased voters or emigrants no longer residing in the municipality) would normally only show up as decreased nominal turnout. Therefore, if we calculate the voter turnout using the estimated adult population instead the number of voters on the voter roll, we get a reliable estimation of “true” turnout – the share of actual adult population participating in the elections.

Figure 1. Changes in total registered voter count relative of the adult population in Serbia and Belgrade

Table 1. Estimated adult population in Belgrade and its municipalities based on 2002, 2011, and 2022 population census

Adult Population	2003	2007	2008	2012	2014	2016	2017	2018	2020	2022	2023	2024
Beograd	1298248	1335458	1344760	1373310	1374597	1375884	1376528	1377171	1379101	1380388	1381031	1381675
Barajevo	20280	21282	21533	22268	22236	22204	22188	22173	22125	22093	22077	22061
Voždovac	126133	129203	129970	133249	135202	137154	138131	139107	142036	143988	144964	145941
Vračar	49733	49075	48910	48246	47905	47564	47393	47223	46711	46370	46200	46029
Grocka	60595	64182	65079	67721	67622	67523	67474	67425	67277	67178	67129	67079
Zvezdara	111187	118200	119953	126564	129265	131967	133318	134668	138721	141422	142773	144124
Zemun	124872	131222	132810	138165	139351	140537	141131	141724	143503	144689	145282	145875
Lazarevac	46086	46916	47124	47500	47006	46511	46264	46017	45275	44781	44534	44287
Mladenovac	42326	43065	43250	43485	42845	42204	41884	41564	40603	39963	39643	39323
Novi Beograd	181612	180870	180684	179476	178171	176867	176215	175562	173606	172301	171649	170997
Obrenovac	56979	58081	58356	58944	58465	57986	57747	57507	56789	56310	56071	55831
Palilula	128029	135192	136983	142929	144077	145225	145799	146373	148095	149243	149817	150391
Rakovica	82317	85928	86831	89263	88711	88159	87883	87606	86778	86226	85950	85674
Savski venac	35305	34323	34077	33117	32668	32219	31995	31771	31098	30649	30425	30200
Sopot	16543	16750	16802	16880	16724	16568	16490	16412	16178	16022	15944	15866
Stari grad	46790	44423	43831	41728	41075	40422	40095	39768	38788	38135	37808	37482
Surčin	31731	33472	33907	35314	35516	35719	35820	35921	36225	36427	36528	36629
Čukarica	137732	143275	144661	148466	147761	147057	146705	146352	145296	144591	144239	143887

Table 2. shows the number of registered voters in Belgrade and individual municipalities. Data for Surcin for 2003 was projected, based on the 2002 population census. This shows that the number of voters on voter rolls in Belgrade is higher than the number of adult population for the entire 2003-2024 period.

Table 2. Number of registered voters in Belgrade and individual municipalities

Voter Totals	2003	2007	2008	2012	2014	2016	2017	2018	2020	2022	2023	2024
Beograd	1445235	1512675	1 534 211	1588427	1607544	1611741	1620072	1599525	1604376	1600462	1613369	1602150
Barajevo	20417	21782	22 176	23725	23936	24090	24101	23527	23750	23516	23745	23562
Voždovac	139770	146469	148 230	153233	158580	161686	162349	161256	160848	161439	163343	162132
Vračar	62172	61965	62 246	63062	63709	63701	63656	60420	63180	63277	64205	62716
Grocka	60490	64804	66 152	70770	71692	68504	73175	71695	73118	72780	73503	72895
Zvezdara	125460	131797	134 580	143868	147428	149813	153679	153929	157701	160479	163528	162254
Zemun	136417	146084	149 445	158206	161108	162819	162574	162962	164951	167209	170188	169245
Lazarevac	48894	50923	51 762	53051	53058	52528	52319	51512	51046	50015	50080	49786
Mladenovac	46234	47447	47 810	48395	48344	48181	47954	44543	46607	45205	45280	44915
Novi Beograd	207017	212356	213 565	213943	214862	213658	213097	211660	206815	204895	204660	203576
Obrenovac	60624	63090	63 561	66155	66421	66556	66500	65320	65371	64201	64468	64015
Palilula	142503	151192	154 604	165092	166792	170087	171630	169586	173314	172734	174559	173257
Rakovica	90237	96571	98 177	102921	103888	104049	103993	102774	101508	100063	99733	99303
Savski venac	44362	44619	44 762	43524	43435	42293	41833	40804	38998	39626	40229	39976
Sopot	16820	17229	17 335	17733	17808	17771	17598	17409	17344	17207	17411	17266
Stari grad	59647	60205	60 042	58910	58240	57187	56745	55727	53608	53832	53910	53487
Surčin	30572	32739	33 856	36263	37538	38095	38421	38245	38703	39048	40087	39826
Čukarica	153599	163403	165 908	169576	170705	170723	170448	168156	167514	164936	164440	163939

Table 3. shows the number of registered voters relative to the corresponding adult population. This shows that, in general, there is a significant surplus of registered voters in both Belgrade and individual municipalities. This can be explained by several reasons, with legal ones including not removing deceased voters from the voter rolls and emigration, where emigrants keep their domicile in Belgrade, while realistically living abroad. They would then legally remain registered to vote in Belgrade, while they would not show up on the population census. Therefore, surplus of registered voters is not necessarily a sign of voter roll manipulation. However, these surplus voters would not be available to vote, and the increase in surplus voters should, absent of voter manipulation, result in a decrease in nominal voter turnout (an increase in passive voter share). On the other hand, if there is a significant surplus of voters on the rolls, and there is an increasing or exceptionally high turnout, this would suggest voter fraud.

Table 3. Voters as % of estimated adult population

Voters as % of Ad. Pop.	2003	2007	2008	2012	2014	2016	2017	2018	2020	2022	2023	2024
Beograd	111.32	113.27	114.09	115.66	116.95	117.14	117.69	116.15	116.33	115.94	116.82	115.96
Barajevo	100.68	102.35	102.99	106.54	107.65	108.49	108.62	106.11	107.34	106.44	107.56	106.80
Voždovac	110.81	113.36	114.05	115.00	117.29	117.89	117.53	115.92	113.24	112.12	112.68	111.09
Vračar	125.01	126.27	127.27	130.71	132.99	133.93	134.32	127.95	135.26	136.46	138.97	136.25
Grocka	99.83	100.97	101.65	104.50	106.02	101.45	108.45	106.33	108.68	108.34	109.50	108.67
Zvezdara	112.84	111.50	112.19	113.67	114.05	113.52	115.27	114.30	113.68	113.48	114.54	112.58
Zemun	109.25	111.33	112.53	114.51	115.61	115.85	115.19	114.99	114.95	115.56	117.14	116.02
Lazarevac	106.09	108.54	109.84	111.69	112.87	112.94	113.09	111.94	112.75	111.69	112.45	112.42
Mladenovac	109.23	110.18	110.54	111.29	112.83	114.16	114.49	107.17	114.79	113.12	114.22	114.22
Novi Beograd	113.99	117.41	118.20	119.20	120.59	120.80	120.93	120.56	119.13	118.92	119.23	119.05
Obrenovac	106.40	108.62	108.92	112.23	113.61	114.78	115.16	113.59	115.11	114.01	114.98	114.66
Palilula	111.31	111.84	112.86	115.51	115.77	117.12	117.72	115.86	117.03	115.74	116.51	115.20
Rakovica	109.62	112.39	113.07	115.30	117.11	118.02	118.33	117.31	116.97	116.05	116.04	115.91
Savski venac	125.65	130.00	131.36	131.42	132.96	131.27	130.75	128.43	125.40	129.29	132.22	132.37
Sopot	101.67	102.86	103.17	105.05	106.48	107.26	106.72	106.07	107.21	107.40	109.20	108.82
Stari grad	127.48	135.53	136.99	141.18	141.79	141.47	141.53	140.13	138.21	141.16	142.59	142.70
Surčin	96.35	97.81	99.85	102.69	105.69	106.65	107.26	106.47	106.84	107.20	109.74	108.73
Čukarica	111.52	114.05	114.69	114.22	115.53	116.09	116.18	114.90	115.29	114.07	114.01	113.94

Considering this, one indication of voter roll manipulation should be changes (annual or periodic) in the voter rolls. Demographic trends are typically stable, and have been stable in Serbia and Belgrade for the past 20 years. Therefore, what we expect to see in voter roll changes are consistent trends over different periods of time. Table 4. shows net changes in numbers of registered voters for Belgrade and individual municipalities. Negative changes are marked in red, and the data is given for periods between two elections, so the individual entries will span different time periods (it is important to keep this in mind).

This table shows relatively consistent trend for 2003-2012 of an increase in number of registered voters, which also corresponds with a period when adult population in Belgrade increased by around 75 thousand. The number of registered voters increased by around 140 thousand, almost double the reported population growth. In the period 2014-2024, the adult population remained relatively stable, increasing by only about 8 thousand, while the number of registered voters fluctuated between 1.59 and 1.62 million, with a net increase of around 14 thousand. These voter number fluctuations are absent in 2003-2012 period, and could be very significant for some municipalities. For instance, in 2017-2018, net 3236 voters were removed in Vracar municipality, while net 2760 were added in 2018-2020, and another net 928 in 2022-2023. This is significant for a municipality with an adult population of 46-48 thousand, and Table 3. shows that these changes represent, around 6%, 7%, and 2.5% of adult population. This is not the only municipality that exhibited sudden changes in the number of registered voters: Tables 3. and 4. also show significant changes for Grocka, Mladenovac, Savski Venac, Zvezdara, and Vozdovac. Although these changes alone should not be an immediate indication of election fraud, they represent a signal that there has been unlawful manipulation with voter registration.

Table 4. Net changes in number of registered voters since last election

Voter changes	2003-2007	2008	2012	2014	2016	2017	2018	2020	2022	2023	2024
Beograd	67440	21536	54216	19117	4197	8331	-20547	4851	-3914	12907	-11219
Barajevo	1365	394	1549	211	154	11	-574	223	-234	229	-183
Voždovac	6699	1761	5003	5347	3106	663	-1093	-408	591	1904	-1211
Vračar	-207	281	816	647	-8	-45	-3236	2760	97	928	-1489
Grocka	4314	1348	4618	922	-3188	4671	-1480	1423	-338	723	-608
Zvezdara	6337	2783	9288	3560	2385	3866	250	3772	2778	3049	-1274
Zemun	9667	3361	8761	2902	1711	-245	388	1989	2258	2979	-943
Lazarevac	2029	839	1289	7	-530	-209	-807	-466	-1031	65	-294
Mladenovac	1213	363	585	-51	-163	-227	-3411	2064	-1402	75	-365
Novi Beograd	5339	1209	378	919	-1204	-561	-1437	-4845	-1920	-235	-1084
Obrenovac	2466	471	2594	266	135	-56	-1180	51	-1170	267	-453
Palilula	8689	3412	10488	1700	3295	1543	-2044	3728	-580	1825	-1302
Rakovica	6334	1606	4744	967	161	-56	-1219	-1266	-1445	-330	-430
Savski venac	257	143	-1238	-89	-1142	-460	-1029	-1806	628	603	-253
Sopot	409	106	398	75	-37	-173	-189	-65	-137	204	-145
Stari grad	558	-163	-1132	-670	-1053	-442	-1018	-2119	224	78	-423
Surčin	2167	1117	2407	1275	557	326	-176	458	345	1039	-261
Čukarica	9804	2505	3668	1129	18	-275	-2292	-642	-2578	-496	-501

3. Trends in voter turnout

Next, we want to examine voting trends with a view of detecting anomalies that would indicate voter manipulation and fraud. We will be looking at two periods: 2003-2012, and 2014-2024. The first period includes elections in 2003, 2007, 2008, and 2012. In all of these elections the major party of the ruling coalition lost significant share of votes and the ruling coalition changed in 2003, 2008, and 2012. This suggests that the extent of voter manipulation and fraud in this period is at least insignificant enough to provide the ruling party with a large enough advantage to keep it in power. This is why we will use this period as our benchmark, assuming that the election manipulation and fraud are insignificant.

In 2014-2024, there has been a single dominant party that maintained a vote share of over 40% in national elections, with numerous allegations of voter manipulation and intimidation, and voter fraud. Therefore, we will examine voter trends in this period against those in 2003-2012 to see if we can detect statistical anomalies indicative of widespread election fraud.

We will conduct this analysis using only voter turnout, measured by the “true” turnout – the voting share of adult population, rather than the nominal turnout of registered voters. This will correct for inaccuracies in the voter rolls and account for changes in population over time.

3.1. Voter turnout correlation within Belgrade

First, we want to establish that the voter turnout in individual municipalities is closely correlated to the turnout in Belgrade as a whole, and that the municipalities behave as a voting cohort of mutually correlated units. Table 5. shows correlation of true voter turnout for Belgrade and individual municipalities for 2003-2012 period. The only municipalities with correlation factor lower than 0.96 for correlation with Belgrade as a whole are Sopot and Surcin with, 0.87 and 0.88, respectively. When looking at mutual correlation between individual municipalities, these two municipalities are the only ones exhibit correlation factors lower than 0.93, with a minimum of around 0.83. However, even for these two municipalities, these are relatively high correlation factors. Given that their population is relatively low with a combined total of just over 40 thousand, their influence on election outcomes is very low and any error introduced by their lower level of correlation with the rest of Belgrade’s municipalities can be tolerated. Our conclusion, based on the data in Table 5, is that the individual municipalities have very high correlation in true voter turnout with Belgrade as a whole, and that their mutual correlation means they should be acting as a single cohort when it comes to voter turnout. Any significant deviation from this can then likely be attributed to outside factors like voter

manipulation and intimidation and election fraud. The high level of mutual correlation is expected, given that the observed elections are of national, and not local, character. Therefore, voter interest in individual municipalities should not vary significantly in different election cycles compared to the overall trends in Belgrade as a whole.

Table 5. Correlation of true voter turnout for Belgrade and its municipalities for 2003-2012.

	BGD	BAR	VZD	VRC	GRC	ZVZ	ZMN	LAZ	MLD	NBG	OBR	PAL	RAK	SV	SOP	SGD	SUR	CUK	
BGD	1																		
BAR	0.964	1																	
VZD	0.998	0.955	1																
VRC	0.982	0.96	0.979	1															
GRC	0.986	0.983	0.977	0.957	1														
ZVZ	0.995	0.935	0.996	0.976	0.969	1													
ZMN	0.991	0.934	0.992	0.951	0.978	0.992	1												
LAZ	0.968	0.984	0.954	0.96	0.98	0.941	0.941	1											
MLD	0.968	0.983	0.953	0.939	0.993	0.943	0.952	0.983	1										
NBG	0.996	0.941	0.997	0.981	0.968	0.998	0.989	0.95	0.942	1									
OBR	0.987	0.989	0.978	0.974	0.996	0.97	0.968	0.985	0.992	0.97	1								
PAL	0.996	0.941	0.996	0.965	0.978	0.997	0.997	0.946	0.955	0.995	0.974	1							
RAK	0.999	0.966	0.997	0.99	0.981	0.994	0.984	0.968	0.964	0.995	0.987	0.992	1						
SV	0.994	0.945	0.995	0.989	0.964	0.995	0.98	0.95	0.938	0.998	0.97	0.988	0.995	1					
SOP	0.873	0.951	0.847	0.878	0.925	0.829	0.835	0.945	0.941	0.834	0.932	0.836	0.874	0.845	1				
SGD	0.989	0.971	0.988	0.995	0.971	0.98	0.965	0.97	0.951	0.987	0.98	0.974	0.994	0.992	0.886	1			
SUR	0.881	0.966	0.858	0.897	0.924	0.836	0.83	0.953	0.949	0.843	0.94	0.843	0.889	0.852	0.975	0.9	1		
CUK	0.996	0.94	0.997	0.971	0.973	0.998	0.994	0.947	0.95	0.997	0.972	0.999	0.994	0.991	0.828	0.978	0.842	1	

Now that we have established that during 2003-2012 voters in Belgrade behaved as a coordinated cohort when it comes to voter turnout, we will examine the same trends for 2014-2024 period. Table 6. shows the correlation of true voter turnout for Belgrade and individual municipalities for 2014-2024. We can see that overall correlation factors decreased across the board, and for some municipalities the correlation decreased so much that they can no longer be considered part of the overall cohort (Lazarevac and Barajevo). This indicates significant changes in voter turnout trends compared to 2003-2012 period, and warrants further in-depth investigation.

Table 6. Correlation of true voter turnout for Belgrade and its municipalities for 2014-2024.

	BGD	BAR	VZD	VRC	GRC	ZVZ	ZMN	LAZ	MLD	NBG	OBR	PAL	RAK	SV	SOP	SGD	SUR	CUK	
BGD	1																		
BAR	0.697	1																	
VZD	0.987	0.678	1																
VRC	0.975	0.62	0.945	1															
GRC	0.907	0.644	0.844	0.888	1														
ZVZ	0.994	0.679	0.992	0.967	0.865	1													
ZMN	0.981	0.638	0.942	0.984	0.937	0.966	1												
LAZ	0.59	0.822	0.514	0.533	0.747	0.537	0.58	1											
MLD	0.906	0.71	0.851	0.921	0.901	0.893	0.934	0.679	1										
NBG	0.989	0.642	0.992	0.966	0.85	0.992	0.96	0.484	0.849	1									
OBR	0.862	0.823	0.793	0.821	0.951	0.819	0.874	0.891	0.894	0.785	1								
PAL	0.995	0.724	0.987	0.952	0.912	0.988	0.964	0.628	0.898	0.979	0.877	1							
RAK	0.994	0.642	0.989	0.962	0.896	0.993	0.975	0.529	0.889	0.989	0.828	0.99	1						
SV	0.981	0.626	0.981	0.975	0.821	0.988	0.956	0.46	0.853	0.994	0.76	0.962	0.975	1					
SOP	0.84	0.671	0.767	0.853	0.96	0.789	0.874	0.804	0.902	0.768	0.937	0.846	0.809	0.751	1				
SGD	0.978	0.673	0.966	0.987	0.835	0.981	0.961	0.517	0.904	0.977	0.793	0.959	0.963	0.99	0.798	1			
SUR	0.861	0.832	0.813	0.874	0.832	0.832	0.876	0.676	0.911	0.818	0.87	0.849	0.822	0.817	0.865	0.871	1		
CUK	0.987	0.641	0.976	0.946	0.908	0.978	0.965	0.568	0.846	0.983	0.845	0.985	0.988	0.965	0.81	0.942	0.79	1	

For now, our conclusion is that for period 2003-2012 Belgrade and its municipalities represent a highly inter-correlated cohort of voters, while for period of 2014-2024 that is no longer the case. There are several municipalities where the decrease in correlation factor is significant.

3.2. Modeling voter turnout in Belgrade

Next step is to create a predictive model of voter turnout in individual municipalities based on the turnout correlation with Belgrade as a whole. For the period of 2003-2012, we have already established high correlation between turnout in individual municipalities and Belgrade as a whole, so we will be looking first for lineal correlation. Linear function $y = a*x + b$ offers an advantage that the slope and the intercept can be interpreted. The slope represents “elasticity” of the voter body: for values <1 , the voter body of the municipality is less elastic than Belgrade as a whole, while for values >1 , the voter body is more elastic than Belgrade as a whole. The intercept represents voting “floor” – if >0 , the voters in the municipality are generally more disciplined than the voters of Belgrade as a whole, turning out in greater numbers at low turnout elections; for values <0 , the voters in the municipality turnout is generally lower in low turnout elections. However, given the overall high correlation across all municipalities, we can expect that the slope values will be relatively close to 1, especially for larger municipalities, and that the intercept will be relatively close to 0.

Table 7. shows an overview of linear fit parameters for all municipalities as a dependence of overall turnout in Belgrade for both 2003-2012 and 2014-2024. There are few immediate observations: for 2003-2012 period, there is generally good fit to linear dependence; for most municipalities, R-squared is greater than 0.94. The values of slope are in 0.81 – 1.18 range, while intercept values are in -5.8 – +7.8 range. This is consistent with the entire voter body in Belgrade behaving as a well-correlated cohort.

Table 7. Comparison of linear correlation of election turnout in Belgrade overall and individual municipalities for periods 2003-2012 and 2014-2024, respectively

Municipality	2003-2012			2014-2024		
	Slope	Intercept	R-squared	Slope	Intercept	R-squared
Barajevo	0.933	2.248	0.946	0.424	32.033	0.486
Voždovac	1.025	-2.958	0.997	1.028	-4.309	0.974
Vračar	1.030	5.189	0.980	1.687	-31.921	0.951
Grocka	0.954	-5.843	0.981	0.595	18.078	0.822
Zvezdara	0.985	-1.408	0.994	1.149	-13.706	0.989
Zemun	0.926	3.030	0.987	0.937	2.201	0.962
Lazarevac	1.115	-1.847	0.958	0.307	54.285	0.348
Mladenovac	0.969	2.646	0.963	0.765	17.218	0.821
N. Beograd	1.046	1.250	0.995	1.263	-12.105	0.979
Obrenovac	0.954	1.899	0.984	0.439	36.469	0.742
Palilula	0.956	-0.565	0.994	1.006	-5.250	0.990
Rakovica	1.017	-1.384	0.998	1.056	-2.543	0.988
Savski venac	1.133	-0.111	0.992	1.462	-23.331	0.961
Sopot	0.904	1.702	0.818	0.304	38.341	0.706
Stari grad	1.175	-0.546	0.984	1.635	-30.319	0.956
Surčin	0.818	7.783	0.840	0.511	29.876	0.741
Čukarica	1.016	-1.676	0.995	1.024	-1.234	0.974

On the other hand, for 2014-2024 period, we see significant deviations from linear correlation and expected values of slope and intercept. Only 5 out of 17 municipalities have values of intercept in -6 – +8 range established for the 2003-2012 period. Other 12 have values that are either lower than -12 or higher than +17. Slope values range from 0.3 to 1.7 – a significantly wider range than 0.8 to 1.2 in 2003-2012. R-squared values are also generally lower, and in some cases linear dependence on turnout in Belgrade as a whole does not exist (Lazarevac and Barajevo). This sudden change in voter behavior cannot be correlated to political events or local character of elections, since most of the elections in this period were either national (parliamentary or presidential) or city-wide (elections for Belgrade City Assembly). There is no reason for voting propensity to change so dramatically across different municipalities, since votes from all municipalities were aggregated, giving equal political motivation to voters across different municipalities.

In addition, the values of intercept in some municipalities indicate large-scale voter intimidation and manipulation: 5 municipalities have intercept values of around 30 or higher. Let us examine the implications of this: the linear model suggests that in the hypothetical situation where turnout in Belgrade as a whole would be 0, the turnout in these 6 municipalities would still be 30% or higher (up to 54% in Lazarevac), and these voters would turn out no matter what. Given that this high voter discipline was missing in 2003-2012 period, we can only conclude that the change in ruling party is the main factor affecting this change, and that this unusually high voter discipline is a result of voter manipulation, most likely intimidation. For all these municipalities, the values of R-squared are lower than in other municipalities, below 0.75, with municipalities with higher values of intercept showing greater deviation from linear dependence.

On the other hand, 3 municipalities have the values of intercept lower than -20, suggesting that their voters would have extremely low turnout in low turnout elections. It is also interesting to note that the R-squared is higher for these municipalities, 0.95-0.96, indicating linear dependence on turnout in Belgrade. This would suggest extremely low voter discipline, or some form of voter manipulation. For 2014-2024 period, low turnout elections were exclusively those where opposition parties boycotted the election, either in part or as a whole. This would mean that low turnout elections were essentially decided in advance, rendering voter manipulation on part of the ruling party unnecessary. However, in high turnout elections, voter manipulation would be a possibility, and this deviation from expected behavior could be an indication of that.

Next, we can examine the slope of linear dependence. There are 6 municipalities with slope values lower than 0.6, with a seventh, Mladenovac, having a value of 0.765. All of these are below the lower end of the range for 2003-2012 period. On the other hand, 4 municipalities have slope values higher than 1.2, above the 1.175 high-end value for 2003-2012 period, with another, Zvezdara, exhibiting a slope of 1.15. Lower values of slope indicate inelastic voter body, and correlated with high intercept values, this would reinforce the suggestion of rampant voter intimidation in these municipalities. High values of slope suggest higher elasticity, suggesting that, when turnout increases in Belgrade as a whole, voters in these municipalities are being added significantly faster than average, sometimes more than 50% faster. This could suggest voter manipulation through addition of ineligible voters (people who are not domiciled in the municipality) or other forms that would add voters that would not turn out under normal conditions.

Based on this data, we can create a linear model to estimate the extent of the election fraud, using 2020 turnout data as the reference point (as the lowest turnout election in the period), and extrapolating voter turnout using 2003-2012 voter turnout linear fit parameters, since this dataset appears to be internally consistent and probably represents true voter intention. The difference between the extrapolated 2003-2012 trend and official voting records can give us a measure of illegally obtained votes across different Belgrade municipalities.

3.3. Voting prediction vs. voting results

Using the linear dependencies detailed in 3.2. we can create projections of election results, based on the overall turnout in Belgrade, and compare them to the actual voting results. Given that there are no “ground truth” numbers when it comes to election fraud in Serbia and Belgrade, the best we can do is provide some estimates and make more general conclusions about the voter trends, potential election fraud and signals in the data indicating the presence and the scale of the election fraud.

We will provide an estimate of potential election fraud based on the following scenario: when actual voter turnout is significantly higher than expected using 2003-2012 voting patterns (the threshold is set at 2% of adult population of a municipality), we classify these voters as “excess voters”. The premise is that these voters would not turn out under normal circumstances and without some kind of incentive, or that these voters are people not captured by the population census, and have no legal right to vote in the municipality (“phantom” voters). In the 1st simulation round we estimate the number of excess voters based on the official turnout for whole of Belgrade. For each following round, we reduce the overall turnout in Belgrade by the amount of excess voters from the previous round and run the model again. This is under the premise that the model will eventually converge to the real number of voters, which would exclude all votes subject to illegal actions (manipulation of the voter roll, “phantom” voters, voter intimidation, etc.). For all municipalities, we ran a total of 11 rounds, and the results are shown below for rounds 1, 2, 3, 8, and 11. Rounds 3, 8, and 11 were chosen because in round 3, model accurately predicted the municipality of Surcin, while round 8 accurately predicted municipality of Grocka for 2022 and 2023, and round 11 accurately predicted municipalities of Sopot and Grocka for 2024.

For 2022. elections, Table 8 shows the results for the first two rounds of projections. These show significant number (more than 2% of adult population) of excess voters in five municipalities, for a total of around 31 thousand voters. These should probably be completely attributed to “phantom voters” – people who have no legal right to vote in these municipalities. It is also clear that these votes are concentrated in traditionally opposition-leaning municipalities, with 3 municipalities showing 10-19% of adult population associated with phantom voters. This already indicates voter fraud at a massive scale, more than enough to change the outcome of the election in these municipalities. However, when we deduct these, likely non-existent, votes from the overall turnout, and run another round of prediction, additional four municipalities show indicators of election fraud and the total number of excess votes is almost 55 thousand. Given the typical turnout in Belgrade of 800-900 thousand, this is a significant percentage of suspect votes, large enough to change the outcome of a relatively close election, which has been the hallmark of Belgrade politics for almost 20 years.

Table 8. Voting intention predictions for 2022 for first two simulation rounds.

	Official Turnout (% of adult pop.)		Projection (1st round)			Projection (2nd round)		
	2020	2022	Proj. turnout	Excess vot, %	Excess vot.	Proj. turnout	Excess vot. %	Excess vot.
Beograd	44.52	67.08	67.08		-31079	64.83		-54613
Barajevo	51.8	58.4	72.85	0.00	0	70.75	0.00	0
Voždovac	40.43	63.12	63.55	0.00	0	61.24	0.00	0
Vračar	41.56	83.5	64.80	-18.70	-8670	62.48	-21.02	-9745
Grocka	47.58	60.81	69.10	0.00	0	66.95	0.00	0
Zvezdara	36.54	62.49	58.75	-3.74	-5286	56.54	-5.95	-8421
Zemun	44.72	65.91	65.60	0.00	0	63.52	-2.39	-3463
Lazarevac	71.02	78.23	96.18	0.00	0	93.67	0.00	0
Mladenovac	53.09	69.73	74.95	0.00	0	72.77	0.00	0
Novi Beograd	42.37	71.22	65.97	-5.25	-9038	63.62	-7.60	-13097
Obrenovac	58.47	67.55	79.99	0.00	0	77.84	0.00	0
Palilula	40.15	62.32	61.72	0.00	0	59.57	-2.75	-4109
Rakovica	44.69	67.67	67.63	0.00	0	65.34	-2.33	-2007
Savski venac	38.3	73.6	63.87	-9.73	-2982	61.32	-12.28	-3764
Sopot	53.47	60.9	73.86	0.00	0	71.82	0.00	0
Stari grad	39.05	78.95	65.57	-13.38	-5104	62.92	-16.03	-6113
Surčin	53.22	62.78	71.68	0.00	0	69.84	0.00	0
Čukarica	44.8	68.12	67.71	0.00	0	65.43	-2.69	-3894

Table 9. shows results of subsequent simulation rounds, where the number of suspect votes increases further, and by round 11, 12 out of 17 municipalities exhibit suspect votes, with their overall number being over 150 thousand. This is roughly 1 in 6 votes in Belgrade, indicating unprecedented scale of election fraud.

Table 9. Voting intention predictions for 2022 for round 3, 8, and 11

	Projection (3rd round)			Projection (8th round)			Projection (11th round)		
	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.
Beograd	63.12		-76168	57.72		-137438	56.22		-156019
Barajevo	69.16	0	0	64.12	0	0	62.72	0	0
Voždovac	59.49	-3.63	-5222	53.96	-9.16	-13194	52.42	-10.7	-15410
Vračar	60.73	-22.77	-10560	55.16	-28.34	-13141	53.61	-29.89	-13859
Grocka	65.33	0	0	60.17	0	0	58.74	-2.07	-1391
Zvezdara	54.86	-7.63	-10795	49.54	-12.95	-18318	48.06	-14.43	-20410
Zemun	61.94	-3.97	-5746	56.94	-8.97	-12981	55.55	-10.36	-14993
Lazarevac	91.77	0	0	85.75	0	0	84.07	0	0
Mladenovac	71.12	0	0	65.88	-3.85	-1538	64.43	-5.3	-2119
Novi Beograd	61.84	-9.38	-16170	56.18	-15.04	-25911	54.61	-16.61	-28619
Obrenovac	76.22	0	0	71.06	0	0	69.63	0	0
Palilula	57.94	-4.38	-6542	52.77	-9.55	-14252	51.33	-10.99	-16395
Rakovica	63.61	-4.06	-3502	58.11	-9.56	-8240	56.59	-11.08	-9557
Savski venac	59.39	-14.21	-4357	53.26	-20.34	-6233	51.56	-22.04	-6755
Sopot	70.28	0	0	65.4	0	0	64.04	0	0
Stari grad	60.92	-18.03	-6877	54.57	-24.38	-9299	52.8	-26.15	-9972
Surčin	68.45	0	0	64.02	0	0	62.79	0	0
Čukarica	63.7	-4.42	-6398	58.21	-9.91	-14332	56.68	-11.44	-16538

Table 10. shows voting intentions for 2023 elections from the first two simulation rounds. Here, again, we see the same five municipalities showing excess votes in the first rounds, with the numbers slightly higher than in 2022. It is interesting to note that the numbers for Vracar and Stari grad are almost the same, even

though the Belgrade-wide turnout is different (68.2% compared to 67.1%), indicating that whatever the process produced excess votes in 2022 was still in place, with minimal expansion, in 2023 elections.

Table 10. Voting intention predictions for 2023 for first two simulation rounds.

	Official Turnout (% of adult pop.)		Projection (1st round)			Projection (2nd round)		
	2020	2023	Proj. turnout	Excess vot. %	Excess vot.	Proj. turnout	Excess vot. %	Excess vot.
Beograd	44.52	68.23	68.23		-33470	65.81		-56154
Barajevo	51.8	61.21	73.92	0.00	0	71.66	0.00	0
Voždovac	40.43	64.03	64.73	0.00	0	62.24	0.00	0
Vračar	41.56	84.83	65.99	-18.84	-8705	63.49	-21.34	-9858
Grocka	47.58	60.37	70.20	0.00	0	67.89	0.00	0
Zvezdara	36.54	63.89	59.88	-4.01	-5719	57.5	-6.39	-9126
Zemun	44.72	68.61	66.67	0.00	0	64.42	-4.19	-6084
Lazarevac	71.02	74.95	97.47	0.00	0	94.76	0.00	0
Mladenovac	53.09	71.46	76.07	0.00	0	73.72	0.00	0
Novi Beograd	42.37	73.46	67.18	-6.28	-10783	64.64	-8.82	-15136
Obrenovac	58.47	67.72	81.09	0.00	0	78.78	0.00	0
Palilula	40.15	62.42	62.82	0.00	0	60.5	0.00	0
Rakovica	44.69	69.58	68.80	0.00	0	66.34	-3.24	-2788
Savski venac	38.3	75.42	65.17	-10.25	-3118	62.43	-12.99	-3953
Sopot	53.47	59.63	74.89	0.00	0	72.7	0.00	0
Stari grad	39.05	80.53	66.92	-13.61	-5146	64.07	-16.46	-6223
Surčin	53.22	67.36	72.62	0.00	0	70.64	0.00	0
Čukarica	44.8	68.49	68.88	0.00	0	66.42	-2.07	-2986

Table 11. shows 2023 predictions for rounds 3, 8, and 11. indicating that the number of suspect votes is higher than in 2022, and that the expected turnout for both 2022 and 2023 elections would roughly be the same. The higher official turnout in 2023 is correlated, in the model, with the higher number of suspect votes, which can be explained by the nature of the elections: while 2022 elections were national elections only, 2023 elections were combined national and Belgrade elections (elections for Belgrade City Assembly), potentially requiring votes to swing the elections in favor of the ruling coalition at the Belgrade City level.

Table 11. Voting intention predictions for 2023 for round 3, 8, and 11

	Projection (3rd round)			Projection (8th round)			Projection (11th round)		
	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.
Beograd	64.16		-79801	58.08		-150303	56.19		-172547
Barajevo	70.13	0	0	64.46	0	0	62.69	0	0
Voždovac	60.56	-3.47	-5032	54.33	-9.7	-14066	52.39	-11.64	-16878
Vračar	61.8	-23.03	-10640	55.53	-29.3	-13535	53.58	-31.25	-14436
Grocka	66.32	0	0	60.52	0	0	58.71	0	0
Zvezdara	55.88	-8.01	-11435	49.89	-14	-19984	48.03	-15.86	-22645
Zemun	62.9	-5.71	-8293	57.27	-11.34	-16471	55.52	-13.09	-19017
Lazarevac	92.93	0	0	86.15	0	0	84.04	0	0
Mladenovac	72.13	0	0	66.23	-5.23	-2072	64.4	-7.06	-2800
Novi Beograd	62.92	-10.54	-18086	56.56	-16.9	-29009	54.58	-18.88	-32409
Obrenovac	77.21	0	0	71.41	0	0	69.6	0	0
Palilula	58.93	-3.49	-5227	53.12	-9.3	-13939	51.31	-11.11	-16650
Rakovica	64.67	-4.91	-4223	58.48	-11.1	-9539	56.56	-13.02	-11194
Savski venac	60.56	-14.86	-4520	53.67	-21.75	-6617	51.53	-23.89	-7270
Sopot	71.22	0	0	65.72	0	0	64.01	0	0
Stari grad	62.14	-18.39	-6953	54.99	-25.54	-9656	52.77	-27.76	-10497
Surčin	69.3	0	0	64.32	-3.04	-1111	62.77	-4.59	-1677
Čukarica	64.75	-3.74	-5392	58.57	-9.92	-14302	56.65	-11.84	-17075

Table 12. shows predictions for 2024 elections, which were not national, but city- and municipality-level only. In addition, part of the opposition boycotted the elections, reducing the turnout, and providing the ruling coalition with a better opportunity to win. This reduced the number of suspect votes in the model, although, interestingly, the numbers at Stari Grad and Savski Venac remained the same. This can be attributed to the fact that, since elections were also at municipality-level, it would have been necessary to maintain vote advantage in each municipality, as well as Belgrade as a whole.

Table 12. Voting intention predictions for 2024 for first two simulation rounds.

	Official Turnout (% of adult pop.)		Projection (1st round)			Projection (2nd round)		
	2020	2024	Proj. turnout	Excess vot. %	Excess vot.	Proj. turnout	Excess vot. %	Excess vot.
Beograd	44.52	53.48	53.48		-27556	51.49		-43924
Barajevo	51.8	51.75	60.16	0.00	0	58.3	0.00	0
Voždovac	40.43	50.64	49.61	0.00	0	47.57	-3.07	-4483
Vračar	41.56	64.18	50.79	-13.39	-6162	48.74	-15.44	-7108
Grocka	47.58	47.51	56.13	0.00	0	54.23	0.00	0
Zvezdara	36.54	48.72	45.36	-3.36	-4840	43.4	-5.32	-7670
Zemun	44.72	53.21	53.01	0.00	0	51.17	-2.04	-2979
Lazarevac	71.02	66.53	81.02	0.00	0	78.79	0.00	0
Mladenovac	53.09	60	61.77	0.00	0	59.84	0.00	0
Novi Beograd	42.37	56.61	51.74	-4.87	-8319	49.66	-6.95	-11888
Obrenovac	58.47	57.24	67.02	0.00	0	65.12	0.00	0
Palilula	40.15	47.12	48.72	0.00	0	46.81	0.00	0
Rakovica	44.69	53.77	53.80	0.00	0	51.77	0.00	0
Savski venac	38.3	58.81	48.46	-10.35	-3127	46.2	-12.61	-3810
Sopot	53.47	53.95	61.57	0.00	0	59.76	0.00	0
Stari grad	39.05	63.21	49.58	-13.63	-5108	47.24	-15.97	-5987
Surčin	53.22	58.04	60.55	0.00	0	58.92	0.00	0
Čukarica	44.8	51.63	53.90	0.00	0	51.88	0.00	0

Table 13. shows 2024 projections from rounds 3, 8, and 11. The overall turnout is significantly reduced, and the number of suspect votes is lower, as well. However, it can be noted that the share of suspect votes is similar in 2022 and 2024, for later projection rounds.

Table 13. Voting intention predictions for 2024 for round 3, 8, and 11

	Projection (3rd round)			Projection (8th round)			Projection (11th round)		
	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.	P. turnout	Ex. vot. %	Ex. vot.
Beograd	50.3		-55328	46.44		-104824	45.03		-121419
Barajevo	57.2	0	0	53.6	0	0	52.28	0	0
Voždovac	46.35	-4.29	-6255	42.4	-8.24	-12027	40.95	-9.69	-14137
Vračar	47.52	-16.66	-7670	43.54	-20.64	-9500	42.09	-22.09	-10169
Grocka	53.1	0	0	49.41	0	0	48.07	0	0
Zvezdara	42.23	-6.49	-9351	38.43	-10.29	-14828	37.04	-11.68	-16830
Zemun	50.07	-3.14	-4579	46.5	-6.71	-9790	45.19	-8.02	-11695
Lazarevac	77.47	0	0	73.17	0	0	71.59	0	0
Mladenovac	58.69	0	0	54.95	-5.05	-1985	53.58	-6.42	-2523
Novi Beograd	48.42	-8.19	-14007	44.38	-12.23	-20913	42.9	-13.71	-23437
Obrenovac	63.99	0	0	60.3	0	0	58.96	0	0
Palilula	45.68	0	0	41.99	-5.13	-7720	40.64	-6.48	-9749
Rakovica	50.57	-3.2	-2743	46.64	-7.13	-6105	45.21	-8.56	-7335
Savski venac	44.85	-13.96	-4215	40.48	-18.33	-5536	38.88	-19.93	-6019
Sopot	58.69	0	0	55.21	0	0	53.93	0	0
Stari grad	45.85	-17.36	-6509	41.31	-21.9	-8209	39.65	-23.56	-8831
Surčin	57.95	0	0	54.79	-3.25	-1190	53.64	-4.4	-1612
Čukarica	50.67	0	0	46.75	-4.88	-7019	45.32	-6.31	-9081

Figure 2. shows how the share of suspect votes changed for each projection round. What we can observe is that there appears to be a good fit to an exponential decay function. When exponential decay function is fit to the data, we can extrapolate the final numbers that the model is converging towards at Belgrade level (Table 14).

Figure 2. Excess votes in Belgrade for each simulation round with exponential decay function fit

These results show the potential scale of election fraud in Belgrade in 2022-2024 elections. The scale seems to have increased from 2022 to 2023/24 from around 19.5% of adult population to around 22.5% of adult population. The suspected “phantom voters” in 5 municipalities (Vracar, Novi Beograd, Zvezdara, Stari Grad, Savski Venac) represent 3.3-3.8% of the overall adult population in Belgrade. If only this was true, that would be enough to invalidate both city-wide elections and municipality-level elections in these 5 municipalities.

Table 14. Exponential decay fit zero for Belgrade for different election years, comparison with round 11 of projections and total number of official votes cast

Year	Exp. Decay Zero	Off. Number of votes	%	11th round	%	1st round	%
2022	-180205	925898	19.46	-156019	16.85	-31079	3.36
2023	-211392	942345	22.43	-172547	18.31	-33470	3.55
2024	-167659	738883	22.69	-121419	16.43	-27556	3.73

In conclusion, the results of the linear model indicate rampant voter fraud and illegal activities in national, city-wide, and municipality-level elections in Belgrade. There is a significant departure from expected voting patterns, and very strong indication of “phantom voters” in at least five municipalities. It is also indicative that all of these municipalities have historically shows strong opposition-leaning tendencies in the past.

For our final examination, we will look more closely into voter turnout trends in three of these five municipalities, to see what overall trends could be indicative of voter fraud.

3.4. Long-term indicators of election fraud in Vracar, Savski Venac, and Stari Grad

Figure 3. shows long-term voter trends in Vracar municipality. There are two clear trends: increase in overall number of registered voters as a % of adult population, and a change in trend of change in passive voters (non-voting registered voters) between 2003-2012 and 2014-2024 period. Overall, in 2003-2012 period both the number of registered voters and the share of passive voters increased, which is consistent with the fact that a significant number of people remained on the voting rolls after death or emigration. The trends align because these voters never showed up as voting population. Therefore, any irregularities in the voter rolls appear to have had no effect on election results.

However, since 2014, while the overall number of registered voters increased as a % of adult population (by about 6%), the share of passive voters declined (if we disregard low-turnout elections where some or all opposition parties boycotted the elections) by about 16% of adult population. The total change in voter turnout is around 22% of adult population for 2014-2024 period. This indicates not only that the voters added to the rolls after 2012 have been turning out to vote, but also that the previously passive voters have been turning out in increasing numbers. Given that the turnout in 2022 and 2023 elections in Vracar was 83.5 and 84.8% of the adult population, respectively, it is unlikely that this is a true reflection of changing voter intentions. It is more likely that, since 2014, increasing voter manipulation and fraud have artificially inflated the turnout in Vracar elections. The trend shown in Figure 3. indicates that the extent of voter fraud has been increasing from 2014 onwards.

Figure 3. Long-term voter trends in Vracar

Figure 4. shows long-term voter trends in Savski venac. The number of registered voters as a % of adult population shows signs of voter roll manipulation in 2014-2024 period. From 2014-2020, the % of registered voters dropped by 8% of adult population, and then bounced back almost completely by 2023. While the number of registered voters remained about the same at the beginning and the end of this period, the number of passive voters declined significantly, by about 15%. This trend is the opposite of the one observed in 2003-2012 election period, indicating again significant irregularities, including likely voting by persons not eligible to vote in this municipality.

Figure 4. Long-term voter trends in Savski Venac

Figure 5. shows long-term voter trends in Stari Grad. There is the same trend in registered voters as a % of adult population, as the one observed in Savski venac, with a decrease of around 3% of adult population in 2016-2020 period, and a rapid increase above previous levels by 2023, for an overall increase in number of registered voters as % of adult population over 2014-2024 period of around 1.5%. In addition, there is also an overall trend in decline in the number of passive voters as % of adult population by around 16%, for a total change of around 17.5 % in active voting population as % of adult population in this period. These changes to the voter roll, coupled with general increase in voter turnout as % of adult population, indicate significant voter manipulation and likely existence of “phantom” voters.

Figure 5. Long-term voter trends in Stari Grad

In general, the trend of decrease and then sudden increase in number of registered voters as % of adult population indicates that a large number of voters are removed from the voter rolls, while equal or greater number of voters are added, probably over this entire period. This would mean that the potential number of

“phantom” voters is greater than the changes observed in the voter rolls, because it is likely that deletion and addition of voters from the rolls occurs over the entire period. Deletion of non-active voters is likely conducted to hide addition of a large number of ineligible voters to the voter rolls to conduct large-scale voter fraud.

4. Conclusions

Even a cursory statistical analysis of voter turnout in Belgrade and its municipalities over 2003-2024 period shows significant signals indicating voter manipulation and outright election fraud. The author would like to highlight the following indicators:

- significant decrease in correlation of voter turnout of Belgrade as a whole and individual municipalities
- significant decrease in correlation of voter turnout between individual municipalities
- deviation from generally linear dependence of voter turnout in Belgrade as a whole and turnout in individual municipalities
- significant changes in slope and intercept of linear fit of dependence of voter turnout in Belgrade as a whole and turnout in individual municipalities
- significant changes in number of registered voters as % of adult population over short periods of time

Linear models allowed us to create projections and estimate the degree of voter fraud over multiple elections in Belgrade in 2022-2024 period. These indicated rampant voter fraud and suggested that as much as 1 in 5 votes cast during this period is tainted by election irregularities.

Finally, analysis of long-term voter trends in three Belgrade municipalities have shown that post-2012 the share of passive voters declined significantly, despite higher or about the same number of registered voters. In addition, significant changes in the number of registered voters indicate significant manipulations of the voter rolls. Combined, these indicate the presence of “phantom” voters – voters that do not hold residence in the municipality (and are not captured by the population census), and are, therefore, ineligible to vote in city-wide and municipality-level elections.

The sum of statistical evidence indicates rampant voter fraud across the majority of Belgrade municipalities, which would invalidate all recent election results and make all national and local governments both illegitimate and illegal.